

MANAGEMENT PROJECT REPORT

ON

Analysis of the Dairy Value Chain Project Implemented by WAVE Foundation

This report is submitted to the Institute of Business Administration, University of Rajshahi for the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Executive Master of Business Administration (EMBA).

Submitted To

Mrinal Kanti Paul

Assistant Professor

Institute of Business Administration (IBA)

University of Rajshahi

Submitted By

Md. Musfikur Rahman

Roll No: **2110085502**

Executive MBA Program, 13th Batch

Session: 2020-2021

Major in Marketing

**Institute of Business Administration
University of Rajshahi**

Date of Submission: 09th July, 2023

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost gratefulness is to Almighty 'Allah'.

I am grateful to a number of individuals for their kind advices, directions, suggestions and co-operation.

Now I would like to express my deepest respect and thanks to my respected teacher and supervisor **Mrinal Kanti Paul**, Assistant Professor, Institute of Business Administration, University of Rajshahi for his guidance, instruction and kind co-operation.

I am in debt to all the individuals of dairy value chain stakeholders including farmers, traders, government officials and so on in Baraigram sub-district, Natore for sharing their views, opinions and experiences and suggestions regarding dairy value chain project analysis.

My gratefulness and special thanks are due to all my teachers for their cordial guidance and helps in different ways.

I am also grateful to my beloved parents, my fellow fellows for their prayers and encouraging words, helping me with their wisdom.

Md. Musfikur Rahman
EMBA, 13th Batch
Roll No. 2110085502
Institute of Business Administration
University of Rajshahi.

LETTER OF ACCEPTANCE

To Whom It May Concern

This is to certify that Md. Musfikur Rahman, Roll No. 2110085502, 13th Batch, EMBA, Session: 2020-2021, Major in Marketing, a student of Institute of Business Administration, University of Rajshahi has completed the Management Project titled **“Analysis of the Dairy Value Chain Project Implemented by WAVE Foundation”** successfully under my supervision.

I wish him every success in life.

09.07.2023

Mrinal Kanti Paul

Assistant Professor

Institute of Business Administration (IBA)

University of Rajshahi (RU)

LETTER OF TRANSMITTAL

09th July, 2023

To,

Mrinal Kanti Paul

Assistant Professor

Institute of Business Administration (IBA)

University of Rajshahi (RU)

It is my great pleasure and privilege to present the management project report titled **“Analysis of the Dairy Value Chain Project Implemented by WAVE Foundation”** which was assigned to me as a partial requirement for the completion of Executive MBA Program.

Throughout the study I have tried with the best of my capacity to accommodate as much information and relevant issues as possible and tried to follow the instructions as you have suggested. I tried my best to make this report as much informative as possible. I however sincerely believe that this report will serve the purpose of management project. I am grateful to you for your guidance and kind cooperation at every step of my endeavor on this report. I shall remain deeply grateful if you kindly take some pan to go through the report and evaluate my performance.

My effort will be rewarded only if it adds value to the research literature.

Sincerely yours,

.....

Md. Musfikur Rahman

EMBA, 13th Batch

Roll No. 2110085502

Institute of Business Administration, University of Rajshahi.

**Institute of Business Administration
University of Rajshahi
Executive MBA Program
Work Schedule for Management Project**

Name : MD. MUSFIKUR RAHMAN Roll No. : 2110085502

Batch : 13th

Signature of Supervisor

1. Consult with Supervisor before starting the Project.

M. Paul
28.03.2023

2. Consult with Supervisor after 4 weeks of starting work with organization and select topic or area of work.

M. Paul
01.06.2023

3. After completing 12 weeks work with organization :

i) Meet supervisor and take necessary advice for report writing.

M. Paul
08.6.23

ii) Meet supervisor and show the work progress.

M. Paul
18.6.23

iii) Submit draft report to supervisor on the 3rd week of report writing.

M. Paul
22.06.23

iv) Finalize the report and submit to IBA, Office.

M. Paul
09.07.23

M. Paul
Professor Dr. Zeennat Ara Begum
Director

CONTENT

	Page Number
Acknowledgement	i
Letter of Acceptance	ii
Letter of Transmittal	iii
Work Schedule of Management Project	iv
Content	v
List of Figures	ix
List of Tables	x
List of Charts	xi
Abstract	xii
CHAPTER-01: INTRODUCTION	1-4
1.1 Background of the study	1
1.2 Statement of the Problem.....	1
1.2 Objectives of the study.....	3
1.3 Importance of the Study.....	3
CHAPTER-02: LITERATURE REVIEW	5-17
2.1 Role of livestock in Bangladesh economy.....	5
2.2 Overview of dairy sub-sector.....	6
2.3 Milk producing animals	7
2.4 Milk production status	8
2.5 Requirement and availability of milk	9
2.6 Milk production of dairy cows of Bangladesh & other countries.....	10
2.7 Import of milk powder	10
2.8 Formal milk marketing channels in Bangladesh.....	11
2.9 Government assistance to the country	12
2.10 Traditional milk trader model	13
2.11 Milk Vita cooperative model	14
2.12 Private entrepreneur model.....	16
2.13 Grameen-Danone model	16

CHAPTER-03: METHODOLOGY	18-19
3.1 Sampling design.....	18
3.2 Data collection	18
3.3 Primary data source.....	18
3.4 Secondary data source.....	19
3.5 Data analysis technique.....	19
3.6 Limitations of the study	19
CHAPTER-04: ORGANIZATIONAL PROFILE	20-43
4.1 Background of WAVE Foundation	20
4.2 Vision, Mission, Values & Goals	20
4.3 Geographic Coverage.....	21
4.4 Human Resources & Offices	22
4.5 Training Center	22
4.6 Social Enterprise	23
4.7 Development Programs & Projects.....	24
4.7.1 Pathways to Prosperity for Extremely Poor People (PPEPP) Project.....	25
4.7.2 Micro Entrepreneurship Project.....	25
4.7.3 Drought Tolerant Variety Rice Seeds Production & Marketing Project	26
4.7.4 Promoting Agricultural Commercialization and Enterprise Project.....	26
4.7.5 Agriculture, Fisheries and Livestock Unit Project.....	27
4.7.6 WAVE Black Bengal Goat Breeding Farm Project.....	27
4.7.7 Alleviation of Poverty through Rearing Hybrid Sheep Project	28
4.7.8 Income Generating through Dumba Rearing Project.....	28
4.7.9 High Value Local Variety Mixed Fish Culture Project and Fish Hatchery....	28
4.7.10 Sustainable Livelihood through Goat and Beef Value Chain Project.....	29
4.7.11 Economic Enhancement through Beef and Goat Market System Project ..	29
4.7.12 Agro Entrepreneur Alliance –AEA Project	30
4.7.13 Community Finance Program	30
4.7.14 Accelerating Sustainable Water and Sanitation Facilities Project	31
4.7.15 Advancement of Informal Sector Employment Project.....	31
4.7.16 Strengthening Resilience of Livestock Farmers	32
4.7.17 Color Broiler and Pekin Duck Project	32

4.7.18 Promoting Agricultural Commercialization and Enterprise Project.....	32
4.7.19 Rural Micro-enterprise Transformation Project.....	33
4.7.20 Safe Vegetables Production and Marketing Project	34
4.7.21 Farmers’ Producer Organization-FPO Strengthening Project	34
4.7.22 Increasing Capacity of Poor Households Project.....	35
4.7.23 Loak Morcha Project.....	36
4.7.24 Youth Assembly Project	36
4.7.25 Out of School Children Education Program	37
4.7.26 Goat Raring for Urban Climate Migrants Project.....	37
4.7.27 Strengthening Community Preparedness Project.....	37
4.7.28 Enterprise Development Program.....	38
4.7.29 Renewable Energy Program	39
4.7.30 Dairy Value Chain Project.....	40
CHAPTER-05: ANALYSIS OF DAIRY VALUE CHAIN PROJECT	44-56
5.1 Key Impacts of the Project Interventions.....	44
5.1.1 Farm size of the dairy farmers	44
5.1.2 Sale volume of dairy feed seller and income from feed sale	45
5.1.3 Sale volume and income of local animal doctors	46
5.1.4 Farmers knowledge improvement on dairy management	47
5.1.5 Increasing milk production of the dairy farms.....	48
5.1.6 Higher price of milk.....	49
5.1.7 Increasing income of the farmers from dairy cow	50
5.1.8 Collecting more milk by collectors and processors	51
5.1.9 Collectors and processors getting available milk.....	52
5.1.10 Improved quality of milk	53
5.2 Additional Impacts of the Project Interventions	54
5.2.1 Changes at inputs and services level.....	54
5.2.2 Changes at milk production level	54
5.2.3 Changes at milk processing level - informal.....	54
5.2.4 Changes at milk processing level - formal.....	54
5.2.5 Changes at milk collection and transport level.....	55
5.2.6 Changes at milk chilling level.....	55

5.2.7 Changes at consumption level	55
5.3 Weaknesses of Dairy Value Chain Project	56
CHAPTER-06: CONCLUSION	57-59
6.1 Findings of the study.....	57
6.2 Recommendations.....	58
6.3 Conclusion	58
REFERENCES	60-61
APPENDIX	62-63

LIST OF FIGURES

	Page Number
Figure-1: Traditional milk trader model	14
Figure-2: Milk Vita cooperative model	15
Figure-3: Private entrepreneur model	16
Figure -4: Grameen-Danone model	17
Figure -5: Dairy value chain	41

LIST OF TABLES

	Page Number
Table-1: The relative contribution of livestock sub-sector to the national economy	6
Table-2: Population of dairy animals and growth rate (%).....	8
Table-3: Yearly milk production and growth rate (%)	9
Table-4: Requirements, production and deficits of milk	10
Table-5: Milk production per animal (kg/lactation)	10
Table-6: Import status of milk and dairy products in Bangladesh.....	11
Table-07: Amount of milk processed by different companies.....	12

LIST OF CHARTS

	Page Number
Chart - 01: Dairy farm size of the farmers.....	44
Chart - 02: Has monthly sale volume of dairy feed seller and income from feed sale increased after project intervention?.....	45
Chart - 03: Has monthly sell volume and income of local animal doctors increased after project intervention?.....	46
Chart - 04: Has dairy value chain project improved farmers knowledge on dairy management?	47
Chart – 05: Has milk production of the dairy farms increased after project intervention?	48
Chart - 06: Does the farmers get higher price of milk now than before?	49
Chart - 07: Does the income of the farmers increase from dairy cow after project intervention?	50
Chart - 08: Do collectors and processors collect more milk now after project intervention??.....	51
Chart - 09: Do collectors and processors get available milk as per their demand now?.....	52
Chart – 10: Do collector and processor think that milk quality has been improved after project intervention?.....	53

ABSTRACT

I have prepared this project report on the dairy value chain project which is implemented by an NGO – WAVE Foundation. Dairy sub-sector provides significant opportunity for income generation and livelihood improvement of the rural mass. There have been wonderful scopes for dairy rearing, dairy product development where large number of people may find employment. Child and maternal undernutrition is still prevalent in Bangladesh and poor dietary diversity is one of the major causes. While milk can contribute to nutritional requirements, currently availability in Bangladesh is 175ml/person/day, whereas recommended consumption is 250ml/person/ day. This study was conducted to analyze existing dairy value chain project of WAVE Foundation, its impacts, strengths and weaknesses along with the opportunity of improvement. It was observed that both formal and informal value chains coexist where milk collectors and chilling centers have a lead role. At the farmers level, there are improvements regarding lot of issues such as increasing number of milking cows, milk production, milk price at local level etc. The relationship among value chain actors at local level has been improved a lot to co-exist themselves for generating mutual benefits. We also found a number of strengths such as large number of high yielding dairy cow and increasing demand of dairy products whereas the weaknesses as lack of farm biosecurity, manure composting initiative and so on. Based on this analysis, a number of recommendations has been placed to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of dairy value chain project further.

Chapter - 01: Introduction

1.1 Background

The dairy value chain project has been implemented by WAVE Foundation since July 2020 in order to improve the livelihoods of dairy farmers. The goal of the project was to increase income of small-scale dairy producers and create more sustainable livelihoods for dairy farmers by incorporating them into a strengthened dairy value chain. The project also generates employment and business opportunities for poor households, other value chain operators (collectors, milk traders, dairy processors, etc.), and supporters (livestock health workers, input suppliers, and government and non-governmental institutions) in the target areas by incorporating them into a strong dairy value chain. The project has been implementing a large number of activities targeted toward improving productivity, increasing access to inputs and increasing access to markets. Therefore, it imperative to analyze the dairy value chain project implemented by WAVE Foundation.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Bangladesh is predominantly an agricultural country and agriculture plays a dominant role in its economy in terms of food security, employment and export earnings. Agriculture sector is comprised of four sub-sectors, e.g. crops, forestry, livestock and livestock is an essential component of the rural economy and the livelihood development of the subsistence farmers. According to department of livestock services (DLS), the livestock sub-sector provides 20% of the population with direct jobs and 45% with part-time jobs. This is particularly important for unemployed youth and women, as well as landless farmers, to lift themselves out of poverty.

At present per capita milk intake is only 175.63 ml while the required amount is 250 ml/day/head (FAO 2022). This indicates a serious shortage of milk instead of the actual demand. Due to huge production deficiency per consumption requirement in Bangladesh, the dairy sub-sector promotion appears to be one of the most potential areas of intervention for ensuring food security, nutrition, and poverty alleviation and import substitution to meet the demand and supply gap. It is worthily mentioned here that dairy farmers have limited access to utilize improve varieties of fodder and management practices. The uses scope of supplementary feed is also limited choice.

The quality of feed is generally poor due to adulteration, very high price and the livestock health services are poor.

Bangladesh is a small country. The current population is 169,532,484 and its density is 1265 persons per square Kilometers. The demand for milk and milk products is increasing because of the rapid increase in population, the spread of education and growing nutrition awareness. National milk production can only meet about 60-70% of the current milk consumption. Among many, the major constraints restricting the expected growth of dairy sub-sector is lack of proper information, inappropriate breeding, feeding, farm management, disease control and inefficient marketing (FAO 2022).

The dairy sector offers a major opportunity to improve nutrition: milk and dairy products are concentrated dietary sources of macro and micronutrients and milk is particularly important for children. In particular, milk can make a significant contribution to meeting the body's needs for calcium, magnesium, vitamin B12, and energy (Muehlhoff, Bennett and McMahon 2020). Pre-school children, and pregnant and lactating women are at highest risk for malnutrition and have highest potential benefit from dairy consumption, due to the nutrition in the milk as well as the potential for income production (CARE 2023). For example, a smallholder dairy initiative by Grameen Bank between 2018 and 2021 improved the nutritional status of 6,000 households. Beneficiaries consumed 0.2–1.0 liter of milk daily. Community-based pro-poor dairy initiatives provided an effective entry point for improving family household nutrition. Dairy industry development aimed at smallholders enhances broader development opportunities for women and young rural people. Empowerment of women has a significant effect on household nutrition outcomes, particularly children's health, wellbeing, and development (Neumann, Harris and Rogers 2021).

Despite nationwide improvements in nutritional status, undernutrition in Bangladesh persists, especially in the form of childhood undernutrition, maternal undernutrition, and different forms of micronutrient deficiencies. The dairy sector offers a major opportunity to improve nutrition: milk and dairy products are concentrated dietary sources of macro and micronutrients and milk is particularly important for children (Lien do et al. 2022). It is worthily mentioned here that dairy farmers have limited

access to utilize improve varieties of fodder and management practices. The uses scope of supplementary feed is also limited choice. The quality of feed is generally poor due to adulteration, very high price and the livestock health services are poor.

1.3 Objectives of the study

- To analyze existing dairy value chain project of WAVE Foundation;
- To suggest key recommendations for improving dairy value project.

1.4 Importance of the Study

Though poverty rate is decreasing day by day, people in Bangladesh are still suffering from undernutrition, malnutrition and severe food safety issues. Hence, the Bangladesh government recognizes the crucial role of agriculture, livestock and fisheries in providing the population with essential and nutritious food and generating employment for a huge number of low-income and vulnerable people living in poor and rural areas. This is particularly important for unemployed youth and women, as well as landless farmers, to lift themselves out of poverty.

The GDP growth rate of livestock has increased over the years representing its potential in rural development and poverty alleviation. Bangladesh is a country facing great challenges in fighting against malnutrition and undernutrition. With a fast-growing population and increasing nutrition awareness, it is important to strengthen livestock development particularly dairy value chain to fulfil the demand (Dangour et al. 2021).

The milk and dairy products help building up vitally strong nations by developing brain and bone of its people. Dairy enterprise is considered as treasure for the economy of Bangladesh, particularly for rural areas (Jabbar, 2022). In Bangladesh, the contribution of livestock sector to agriculture share of Gross Domestic Product was 13% during 2021-2022. Besides, according to FAO, the per capita average yearly milk consumption in Bangladesh is the lowest in South Asia because of higher cost of production and lower yield compared to any other south Asian countries. (FAO, 2022). Rearing dairy cow is one of the most important investments a farmer can make to improve their socio-economic condition because of the valuable nutritional milk produced and diversify farming activities. In Bangladesh, the annual national production of milk is 13.5 million

tons and the annual demand is 17 million tons, out of which 97% is produced in rural areas. The quantity of national milk production can only meet about 60-70% of the actual demand for milk of the population (DLS, 2021).

The development of the dairy sector in the country is hindered by a number of technical, institutional and socioeconomic constraints. Development of small-scale dairy sector is necessary to create employment opportunity and increase income for the people in rural areas. Therefore, the impacts of milk and milk related products are multifaceted, and it depends on a large number of socio-economic and nutrition factors. Under this backdrop, the dairy value chain project was initiated by WAVE Foundation for improving socio-economic condition of the dairy farmers. Therefore, the study has been planned to understand the actual impacts and results of the dairy value chain project on the life and livelihood of value chain actors including farmers.

Chapter – 02: Literature Review

2.1 Role of livestock in Bangladesh economy

Livestock plays a significant role in traditional farming, supply of food of animal origin and extensive employment generation. Nowadays government and private sector are working together to meet the demands of adequate and safe meat, milk and egg of the country. Since the eighties, contribution of livestock sector is increasing day by day, opportunity of employment, number of commercial farm and production of livestock increased surprisingly. Demands of animal origin food are increasing due to rapid economic development, reduction of hardcore poor and health consciousness among the people in the country. It can solve the problems of malnutrition, unemployment, empowerment of women, growth of fertility of agricultural land, making a talented nation and earning foreign exchange. Meat, egg and milk play a vital role in meeting the demands food of animal origin in our everyday life.

Hides and skins are other non-edible valuable animal products. The production of hides and skins in Bangladesh is quite high. The domestic use of hides and skins for leather production is low in the country. About 81% of the total production is exported in the form of 'wet blue' leather and leather products (Saadullah, 2020). There are several hundred tanning and finishing industries in the country. Several thousand people are engaged full time in this industry. Notable leather-made commodities are shoes, suitcase, bags, tents, etc.

Cow dung is an important source of natural manure and fuel. About 80 million m tons of cow dung is produced annually. Cow dung is also used to produce biogas. Moreover, the bones, horns, and hooves from ruminants have great economic value. Bangladesh earns' significant amount of foreign exchange by exporting crushed and uncrushed bones every year.

Among the four agricultural sub-sectors, most of the development efforts in the past were concentrated on crop production, and therefore, the livestock sub-sector remained underdeveloped. Although proper emphasis was not given in the past on livestock sub-sector but still this sub-sector is growing due to the efforts of public entrepreneurs and playing a very vital role for the development of agriculture in conjunction with crops.

At present, the magnitude of contribution of the livestock sub-sector to country's gross domestic product (GDP) is 2.58 percent (BER, 2022). The growth rate of GDP in 2021 for livestock was the highest of any sub-sector at 4.5%, compared to 3.2% for crop and 2.3% for the fisheries sub-sector (MOFL, 2022). These changes have been accelerated by a rapid growth in demand for livestock products due to increases in income, rising population number and urban growth. This phenomenon has been referred to as the Livestock Revolution (BER, 2022).

The relative contribution of livestock to national GDP and their changing patterns during the last five years are shown in **Table 1**.

Table-1: The relative contribution of livestock sub-sector to the national economy

In total agricultural gross domestic products (GDP)	14.07%
In countries gross domestic products (GDP)	2.73%
Foreign exchange earnings (from hides and skin)	3.67%
Full time employment	25%
Part time work provision	50%

Source: DLS (2022)

Contributions from the livestock sub-sector to the economy have been largely underestimated in the past although the sub-sector is providing for a wide range of human needs. The challenge now is to increase the productivity of livestock and improve the quality of livestock products and provide access to markets to assist in maintaining food security and relieving poverty while maintaining the physical environment and protecting human health from Zoonotic diseases.

2.2 Overview of dairy sub-sector

Rearing dairy cow is a profitable occupation as no part of the bovine is wasted as live or dead. In Bangladesh, Dairying is nearly always a part of mixed farming system and is the prominent source of income generation (Saadullah, 2020). Hemme *et al.* (2020) mentioned that milk production is a livestock enterprise in which small scale farmers can successfully engage in order to improve their livelihoods. Dairy industry can be made an important sector economy after garments industry. The dairy sector in

Bangladesh is very significant for poverty alleviation, employment generation, food and nutrition improvement, women's empowerment and earning foreign exchange. It provides milk, meat, hide and skin in addition to providing of non-human farm energy needed for ploughing, crushing, and transportation. here's huge demand of dairy products - like pasteurized and powdered milk, yogurt, cheese and butter in Bangladesh. Due to low-production, supply constraints and lack of optimal quality enhancement the country has to import powdered milk.

The dairy sector of Bangladesh has certain characteristics, common to many developing countries in Asia. Bangladeshi dairy farmers are pre-dominantly small scale producers with a majority of them owning small amount of land and one to three animals. Unlike many major developed dairying countries where grain/pasture is used for feeding, the dairy animals in Bangladesh are largely fed on agricultural by-products and residues. Household members carry out most of the dairy farming operations by themselves, with women contributing significantly to these operations. The demand for milk and value added a milk product is increasing rapidly. For these reason, dairy development has assumed a position of paramount importance in the rural economy of Bangladesh. It is essential that this sub-sector, like other sub-sector of tropical agriculture should be modernized and made more productive as quickly as possible.

2.3 Milk producing animals

Cattle, buffalo and goat are considered as dairy animals of the country. The breeds of livestock available in Bangladesh are as follows: Cattle: (i) local breed of cattle- non-descript indigenous type, Red Chittagong Goyal, Pabna Cow; (ii) Exotic: Hariana, Sindhi, Shahiwal, Jersey, and Holstien-Friesian; (iii) Hybrid: Bos indicus' Bos taurus. Buffalo: (i) River type, (ii) Swamp type, (iii) River' Swamp type. Goat: (i) Black Bengal, (ii) Jamuna Pari, (iii) Crossbred- Black Bengal' Jamuna Pari. Sheep: non-descript indigenous type.

Out of total milk production, about 90% is coming from dairy cows and the remaining 10% from buffaloes and goats (DLS, 2023). According to the latest record of DLS (2023), there are about 23.121 million cattle, 1.394 million buffaloes and 24.149 million goats in the country (Table 2). Among the total cattle population, about 6.0 million are dairy cattle of indigenous (about 85-90%) and crossbreds (about 10-15%) cows.

Indigenous cows consisted of a) Non-descriptive type, b) Red Chittagong cattle, c) North Bengal Gray and d) Munshiganj white cows. On the other hand, crossbred cows are the results of crossing between local cows and exotic bulls. Exotic bulls are mainly Holstein and Jersey, although in the past-Sindhi and Sahiwal was the major component of breeding bulls. Cows are inseminated through artificial insemination and semen is collected either from bulls reared by CCBS, BRAC and Milk Vita in the country or imported from abroad (Islam and Akbar, 2022). However, the growth rate of cattle is slower as compared to buffalo and goat.

Table-2: Population of dairy animals and growth rate (%)

Year	Cattle		Buffalo		Goat	
	Number	Growth	Number	Growth	Number	Growth
2012-13	22.53	-	1.01	-	17.69	-
2013-14	22.60	0.31	1.06	4.95	18.41	4.07
2014-15	22.67	0.31	1.11	4.72	19.16	4.07
2015-16	22.80	0.57	1.16	4.50	19.94	4.07
2016-17	22.87	0.31	1.21	4.31	20.75	4.06
2017-18	22.90	0.31	1.26	4.13	21.56	3.90
2018-19	22.98	0.33	1.30	3.49	22.40	3.90
2019-20	23.051	0.15	1.35	3.85	23.275	3.91
2020-21	23.121	0.30	1.394	3.26	24.149	3.76
Average growth rate (%)		0.32		4.15		3.97

Source: DLS (2022)

2.4 Milk production status

Milk production trend along with its growth rate (%) is shown in **Table-3**. Although Department of Livestock Services (DLS) is trying hard to increase the milk production in the country practically the result is not satisfactory. The production of milk was expected to show a significant increase during the perspective plan period (MOFL, 2022). It was estimated that milk production will increase from 1.41 million metric tons to 3.34 MMT and 5.38 MMT. But the target could not be achieved. Although milk

production was increasing slowly up to 2017-18 thereafter production dropped sharply from 2.65 MMT to 2.29 MMT. This indicates that in the year 2018-19 growth rate of milk production was negative (-13.89%), although growth rate was positive (+16.23%) in 2017-18 (**Table 3**). Thereafter in the year 2019-20, milk production increased by 3.5% but dramatic increase in milk production is seen (24.89%) in the year 2020-2021, which is the highest increment rate during the last ten years.

Table-3: Yearly milk production and growth rate (%)

Year	Milk	
	Production (MMT)	Growth rate (%)
2012-13	1.82	-
2013-14	1.99	9.34
2014-15	2.14	7.54
2015-16	2.27	6.06
2016-17	2.28	0.44
2017-18	2.65	16.23
2018-19	2.29	-13.89
2019-20	2.36	3.5
2020-21	2.95	24.89
Average growth rate (%)		6.76

Source: DLS (2022) and growth rate was calculated

2.5 Requirement and availability of milk

It is recommended that an adult person requires at least 250 ml milk every day. But our availability is only about 54.65 ml/h/d. This indicates that we are in serious shortage of milk. Total milk production of the country as per 2020-21 data is 2.95 MMT/year but our requirement is about 13.32 MMT/year. The country is running with deficiency of milk of about 78% (**Table 4**).

Due to shortage huge amount of milk in our country, private enterprises are taking importing milk from abroad. Milk is mainly imported from abroad in powder form. The powder milk which is coming in this country with the cost of huge amount of foreign currency is not totally safe for human consumption as because of presence melamine,

a hazardous chemical dangerous for human health was detected in the powdered milk in China.

Table-4: Requirements, production and deficits of milk

Status	Per day	Per year
Requirements	250 ml/h/d	13.32 MMT
Production/Availability	175.63 ml/h/d	08.60 MMT
Deficiency	74.37 ml/h/d	04.72 MMT

Source: DLS (2022)

2.6 Milk production of dairy cows of Bangladesh & other countries

Milk producing ability of Bangladeshi cows and buffaloes are very poor in comparison with other countries. **Table-5** represents the milk production status of different countries.

Table-5: Milk production per animal (kg/lactation)

Country	Cattle	Buffalo
Bangladesh	207	407
Bhutan	257	400
Nepal	415	850
Sri Lanka	627	496
India	987	1450
Pakistan	1195	1909
Australia	4926	-
New Zealand	3974	-

Source: FAO, 2022

2.7 Import of milk powder

There is a relationship between powdered milk and the liquid milk market. If powdered milk sales plummet, liquid milk sales jump. Therefore, there are no alternatives to ease the import of powdered milk and raw materials for packaging. The import issues should be settled promptly. Among other sources, milk is one of the major sources for protein diet across the globe. However, due to inadequacy between demand and supply of milk,

Bangladesh has to import milk to compensate the demand (**Table 6**). Milk is mainly imported in powder form. It is likely that there are scopes to enter diseased animals to Bangladesh and might be a cause of spreading contagious disease.

Table-6: Import status of milk and dairy products in Bangladesh

Period	Amount in Crore Taka
2009-2010	302
2010-2011	333
2011-2012	339
2012-2013	353
2013-2014	359
2014-2015	532
2015-2016	489
2016-2017	572
2017-2018	943
2018-2019	664
2019-2020	736
2020-2021	1153
2021-2022	1750
Source: Statistical Department, Bangladesh Bank 2022	

The microbial status of the most commercially available powdered milk were studied by Rahman, *et al.* (2021) and found that total bacterial population were higher than the standards due to contamination during handling, transportation and storage. High number of Coliform bacteria was detected in imported milk powder which indicated that they might have been either contaminated by fecal materials or improper storage or unhygienic packaging.

2.8 Formal milk marketing channels in Bangladesh

Apart from the informal or traditional milk marketing system in Bangladesh, several milk and milk product enterprises started milk marketing since long. Among the milk enterprises, Milk Vita is probably the first venture to initiate milk marketing through

cooperative farming in Bangladesh. The market share of different milk enterprises is shown in **Table-07**.

Milk being perishable item, needing timely and special attention to market, makes the marketing more difficult. Generally, rural milk producers sell their surplus milk to various marketing intermediaries prevailing locally who in turn sell the milk to the individual consumers, restaurants & tea stalls in the urban area. In this process marketing intermediaries buy the milk from the farmers at a cheap price and are said to appropriate large profit. Lack of effective marketing organization in the grass-root level is a drawback for the farmers' position in selling milk.

Table-07: Amount of milk processed by different companies

Processing companies	Establishment year	Average milk collection (liters/day)	Market share (%)
BMPCUL	1973	200	52.08
BRAC dairy	1988	80	20.83
PRAN dairy	2001	40	10.42
Amomilk	1996	10	2.60
Bikrampur dairy	1998	10	2.60
Ultra Shelaida dairy	1998	10	2.60
Aftab dairy	1998	8	2.08
Tulip dairy	1998	3	0.78
Grameen/CLDDP	1999	7	1.82
Grammen-Danone	2007	1	0.03
Rangpur dairy	2007	8	2.08
Akij dairy	2007	4	1.04

Source: Adopted from Raha (2022) and other sources

2.9 Government assistance to the country

The Bangladesh government has set up quite a few agencies to cater services to the needs of the livestock industry. First, there is the Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock which is responsible for the policies and overall direction of the industry. In addition,

the Department of Livestock Services (DLS) is responsible for providing extension services to farmers. A third body is the Bangladesh Livestock Research Institute (BLRI) which is responsible for conducting research on breed improvement and development of feeding strategies for dairy animals.

The low-cost loan scheme for dairy farming has a positive impact on the rural economy. Women and marginal farmers are prioritized in extending loans, and the upazila office of the livestock services department oversee the process to ensure proper use of the money on the borrowers' part. Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock has declared, National Livestock Development Policy (MOFL 2022) , with emphasis on the following areas for the dairy development of country:

- ✓ Cooperative dairy development (Milk Vita model) would be expanded in potential areas of the country;
- ✓ Successful pro-poor models for community-based smallholder dairy development including appropriate contact farming schemes would be replicated;
- ✓ Smallholder dairy farming integrated with crop and fish culture would be promoted;
- ✓ Supply chain based production and marketing of milk and milk products would be promoted;
- ✓ A National Dairy Development Board would be established as a regulatory body promote dairy development;
- ✓ “National Dairy Research Institute” would be established to carry out research in various aspects of dairying.

2.10 Traditional milk trader model

Bangladesh, like other South Asian countries, has a dairy system characterized by small-scale operations, integrated with crops and other off-farm activities. Dairying is considered a major source of nutrition and income, and offers good opportunities for both farm families and non-farm rural and urban employment. Consequently, several dairy development programmes and models have been implemented for improving the

dairy sector. The gradual shift from subsistence to market-oriented dairy units demands more advanced knowledge and dairy technology.

Smallholder milk producers sell milk directly to consumers or milk supplier/middlemen at local markets. The middlemen cater to the demand of sweetmeat shops, bakeries, consumers, more distant markets and vendors. They pay producers less for their milk than other models, such as those described in the following sections. In many cases, the middlemen provide loans to smallholders with interest rates.

At the present, majority of farmers who are mainly small holder dairy owners selling their milk by traditional (informal) marketing system and cooperative milk marketing system. In traditional marketing system, milk is sold on the basis of volume without giving any emphasis on fat content of milk. Usually, vendors and other milk collectors are involved in this marketing system. For this reason, farmers could not get fair price for their milk. At the same time there is no guarantee of fixed price and milk price varies day to day. Model for traditional milk marketing system is shown in figure 01.

Figure-1: Traditional milk trader model

Source: Islam and Akbar (2022)

2.11 Milk Vita cooperative model

In Bangladesh, Milk Vita has successfully developed a cooperative milk production model like AMUL, India beyond existing traditional or informal systems as well as combating all sorts of identified challenges. Milk Vita is a milk production company that produces milk under its own name. It is owned by Bangladesh Milk Producers Co-operative Union Limited, a cooperative managed by itself. Milk Vita has 70 percent market share of liquid milk in Bangladesh.

Dairying in Bangladesh is generally characterized by small-scale, widely dispersed and unorganized milk animal holders, low productivity, lack of assured year-round remunerative producer price for raw milk, inadequate basic infrastructure for provision of production inputs, services and above all lack of professional management practices. Milk Vita not only broke the monopoly of the milk buyers but, more significantly, it greatly increased the region's milk production. The Project of milk vita includes milk producers become directly involved in the management of Milk Vita, milk production input and support services need to be self-funding, milk production enhancement and collection should directly be targeted.

The Milk Vita Cooperative model was adapted from the world-renowned Anand Model in India. It modestly started in the mid-1970s by providing very poor, often landless, households in remote rural areas with a complete package of milk production-enhancing technologies, organizational skills and a milk collection-processing-marketing system. It has since grown into a successful commercial dairy enterprise, collecting from large smallholder members of primary village cooperatives and then processing and distributing the milk to all major cities in the country.

Figure-2: Milk Vita cooperative model

Source: Joshi (2022)

Milk Vita has developed cooperative marketing system in Bangladesh. In this system payment of milk is done on the basis of fat content of milk at a fixed price. At the village level dairy farmers are organized society. Individual members deliver milk to a

common collection point and from the collection point milk is brought to a chilling plant. Milk Vita has about 24 plants in the country and from their chilling plants; milk is collected daily to its central factory at Mirpur (Dhaka). In this system, farmer's exploitation by middlemen is avoided. Moreover, farmers get bonus price at the end of each year on their supplied milk and also get lot of other facilities for rearing their cows. Payment of milk is done on the basis of fat percent of milk. Model for Milk Vita system is shown in Figure-2.

2.12 Private entrepreneur model

Private dairies, some owned by NGOs such as BRAC, Akiz and PRAN, usually operate through milk supplier-middlemen (Ghoshes or Dudhwalas) in place of rural groups or cooperatives. They collect milk for the assigned dairy and smallholders involved in the system do not receive any value addition benefit, just the basic price for their milk. A number of private companies and NGO's follow the same basic procedure of collecting milk from farmers through their agents who in turn collect milk from farmers. The price of milk is set on the basis of its fat content.

Figure-3: Private entrepreneur model

Source: Islam and Akbar (2022)

2.13 Grameen-Danone model

Grameen-Danone Foods Limited was set up in 2006 and is in an innovative joint social venture between the Grameen Bank and Danone, a large French multi-national dairy corporation renowned for its functional Bio-Yoghurts. It's a community-based enterprise, collected from the poor farmers under the concept of social business. They prepare Yoghurts and market both rural and urban markets. The first social venture is Grameen Danone Foods, which produces low-cost, fortified yogurt for sale in rural

communities. A pilot dairy enterprise was set up in Bogra. The long-term plan is build rural enterprises in ten other disadvantaged areas of Bangladesh. The Bogra enterprise began in February 2007.

Figure-4: Grameen Danone model

Source: Grameen Danone Report, 2021

Chapter – 03: Methodology

3.1 Sampling Design

- Population: A total of 2150 beneficiaries: 2000 dairy farmers, 50 feed sellers, 50 animal doctors and 50 milk collectors and processors who are direct beneficiaries of dairy value chain project.
- Sampling Size: A total of 50 samples: 20 dairy farmers, 10 animal feed sellers, 10 local animal doctors, and 10 milk collectors and processors as respondents.
- Sampling Area: Baraigram Upazila of Natore district.
- Sampling Technique: Nonprobability convenience sampling technique.

3.2 Data Collection

Primary and secondary sources of data have been used to prepare the report. I took around 5 days to complete the interview survey.

3.3 Primary Data Source

Interview Survey

Primary data has been collected from the enlisted respondents such as animal feed sellers, animal doctors, dairy farmers, milk collectors and processors through fulfilling a questionnaire which has been finalized with pre-test.

Interview Questionnaire

A structured interview questionnaire was prepared with open and close ended questions to collect primary data from respondents. There have been several questions considering the variations of respondents aiming at collecting views and opinions toward dairy value chain project.

Key Informant Interview (KII)

Qualitative information regarding the impacts and weaknesses of dairy value chain project along with key recommendations was collected and cross checked with the discussion of relevant stakeholders such as 01 government officials from department of livestock services and 01 livestock expert from private company Renata Animal Health.

3.4 Secondary Data Source

The major reviewed sources/documents included websites, reports, case studies of various natures, national & international journals, books and other relevant documents.

3.5 Data Analysis Technique

- Excel software has been used to analyze data.
- Different tables, graphs and charts have been used to present results and findings.

3.6 Limitation of Study

This study limits only on the available published data and certain degree of primary information collected through interview survey. Due to time limitation, many aspects could not be covered in the present study as it is a vast subject. The respondents sometimes were found non-cooperative with the interviewer.

Chapter - 04: Organizational Profile of WAVE Foundation

4.1 Background of WAVE Foundation

WAVE Foundation is a national NGO established in 1990. Since its establishment, the organization has been implementing multifaceted activities for the socio-economic development of the poor and marginalized as well as the establishment of universal human rights and good governance. Besides, the organization is conducting issue-based policy advocacy and campaigns. WAVE is driven by its motto “Together for Better Life” towards the vision of establishing a “A just and Prosperous society”. It is now working directly with more than 17 million people all over the country and making significant contributions to the realization of the country’s 7th 5-year plan and the achievement of the sustainable development goals.

4.2 Vision, Mission, Values and Goals

VISION

A Just and Prosperous Society

MISSION

WAVE Foundation promotes rights and entitlement of the people. Organization’s priority is to include the poor and marginalized people in the development interventions towards sustainable livelihood, empowerment, equality, democratic governance and climate resilience.

VALUES

Integrity: We demonstrate our integrity through our commitment, honesty and work.

Mutual respect: We hold mutual respect irrespective of position, age, gender, ethnicity and religion.

Accountability: We demonstrate accountability and fairness by abiding rules and policies at work.

Professionalism: We acknowledge professionalism at all aspects of work and life.

Teamwork: Besides our individual responsibilities we work in team to perform tasks.

STRATEGIC GOALS

Funds Received from Donor Agencies

British Council	Ministry of Primary and Mass Education
Christian Aid	Norec (Former FK Norway)
Heifer International-USA	Oxfam
IDCOL	PKSF
IDE	The Asia Foundation
GIZ	UNDP and LGD
Manusher Jonno Foundation	Water.org

Source: WAVE Foundation Annual Report, 2022

4.3 Geographical Coverage

19 Districts: Khulna, Chuadanga, Meherpur, Kushtia, Jhenaidah, Magura, Jashore, Satkhira, Bagerhat, Rajshahi, Pabna, Natore, Barishal, Patuakhali, Barguna, Bhola, Dhaka, Manikgonj and Narayangonj.

4 Divisions: Khulna, Rajshahi, Barishal and Dhaka.

4.4 HR and Offices

Human Resources

A total number of 1978 of employees are working in WAVE Foundation at various levels. 766 of them are female and 1212 are male.

Offices

WAVE Foundation has its Head Office in Dhaka and a Base Office at Chuadanga district. It has 06 Regional, 25 areas, 127 Units and 45 Projects Offices.

4.5 Training Center

General Training Center

To develop human resources including staff, partners, beneficiaries and other stakeholders, WAVE Foundation has incorporated training as an integral part of all programs. It has its own training center in Chuadanga equipped with all the necessary and modern supports including accommodation facility. Through the training center, WAVE also offers various need-based training courses for other NGOs and non-project participants. WAVE has deployed appropriate, qualified and professional training staff in the center. Apart from the training center staff, WAVE has a Pool of Resource Persons to conduct various training sessions. Deputy Executive Director, Assistant Executive Director, Program/Project Coordinators and Deputy Program/Project Coordinators of various programs/projects, Head of Finance & Administration, Head of Internal Audit, Head of Monitoring Division, etc. of WAVE belong to the Pool of Resource Persons. Some external reputed persons of various organizations and local government expert individuals also belong to the Pool of Resource Persons who conduct various training sessions on need basis.

Trade Training Center

The main objective of the Trade Training Center is to develop human resources in line with the market needs through skill development training and ensure more productive wage-based employment and self-employment at the end of the training. It increases financial capacity of the participants so that they are able to sustainably improve their quality of life. For achieving the goal & objectives, it organizes and facilitates 3 months residential Competency Based Training-CBT and job placement (wage-based /self-employment) for the certified participants. WAVE Trade Training Center provides

training with support from Bangladesh Technical Education Board and about 72% trainees have got job or are self-employed. The training supports provided by WAVE are: Computer Office application, Sewing Machine Operation, Mobile Phone Servicing, Electrical Installation and Maintenance and Graphic Design.

4.6 Social Enterprises

Sheep Farm

To ensure food security and self-employment of the poor and the hardcore poor, WAVE established sheep farm in Meherpur and Patuakhali districts from 2015 and 2017 respectively. The objectives of this farm are to conduct necessary adaptive research to make the sheep rearing profitable; conserve the genetic purity of local improved and cross-breed sheep and expand the verities to the community level.

ANGKUR Crafts

Angkur Crafts is an enterprise of WAVE Foundation that aims to support poor and underserved families by creating opportunities for them to become small entrepreneurs and building market linkage of their products especially crafting and clothing. Women are particularly encouraged to join this platform. It has been playing significant role for the women to achieve skills and grow as entrepreneurs. Since its inception, around 12,355 pieces of hand-stitched clothes produced by these women. Another important thing is that Angkur Crafts is also working to set up a market linkage to allow the products of these small producers find buyers. At present, it has outlets at Chuadanga and Meherpur district. Due the growing interest of customers the enterprise is expanding outreach of its products in targeted areas.

ANGKUR Seeds

Quality Seed is the precondition for bumper Agricultural Production. Being an Agricultural country, it uses approx. 30% quality seeds in agricultural production while the rest of the 70% seeds are below standard which has negative impact on our gross agricultural production. ANGKUR Seeds is an initiative dedicated to the sustainable development of agricultural sector through ensuring available production, efficient processing and planned marketing of quality Crop Seeds to meet the Farmer's demand. WAVE introduced this brand in 2009 and now it is registered under the government authority. ANGKUR Seeds dedicated to develop capacity of farmers introducing new

technologies, producing and marketing high-yielding varieties of rice and onion seed (year-round) with remarkable success. A significant number of contact farmers are currently producing and marketing rice and onion seed under this enterprise.

ANGKUR Machineries

Extending affordable agro machineries to the farmers is the single most prerequisite to take a leap from manual to mechanization of our agriculture which can radically increase the gross agricultural production. ANGKUR Machineries is an enterprise of WAVE Foundation that aims at complementing WAVE's commitment towards the development of agriculture sector. It established in 2016 to be an active part of the mechanization of Bangladesh's agriculture sector. It offers a wide range of agro machineries to the farmers i.e. Power Tiller, Thresher, Chopper, Reaper, Harvester, Shallow Pump, Sprayer and so on at an affordable price. WAVE works in close collaboration with Department of Agriculture Extension and well known agro research firms to ensure its tools are environment friendly and efficient. Since its inception, ANGKUR Agro Machineries have been contributing to higher agricultural yield and better earning for the farmers. WAVE sets 2 outlets of Angkur Machineries in Darsana, Chuadanga and Natore.

4.7 Development Programs and Projects

It is a major challenge to establish a world without hunger, poverty, social injustice, and discrimination. This challenge /or obstacle is also prevalent in our country. As a development organization, WAVE Foundation is developing and carrying out a multifaceted action plan to establish a society that is poverty free and built on equality to overcome these challenges or obstacles from the inception. The completion of this challenging task necessitates diligent effort through the adoption of integrated action plans and processes. WAVE Foundation is assisting in the development of small and medium enterprises centered on agriculture and small business to generate employment possibilities for all people, irrespective of gender or ethnic identity, especially for the most marginalized groups of society. Following a holistic, multi-dimensional, and equitable process as part of sustainable and resilient livelihood development, projects are undertaken with greater emphasis on economic growth and empowerment of the extremely poor, persons with disabilities, food security and nutrition, justice for climate risk victims, and gender equality in vulnerable districts. Besides, projects are

undertaken with a greater focus on economic growth for the empowerment of the extremely poor, people with disabilities, sufferers of the food crisis and nutrition, justice for survivors of climate risk, and gender equality in vulnerable districts, following a holistic, multidimensional, and equitable process as part of sustainable and resilient livelihood development. Having access to healthcare and education is necessary for sustainable and resilient livelihoods. In this backdrop, we are accelerating the process for people to have easier access to education, and healthcare services, particularly for children and pregnant women. WAVE Foundation implements following development programs and projects:

4.7.1 Pathways to Prosperity for Extremely Poor People (PPEPP) Project

Pathways to Prosperity project supports extremely poor people to connect with mainstream economic growth and jobs for sustainable development. The objectives of the project are to enable two million people (500,000 households) to exit from extreme poverty for good and support the development of stronger national institutions & systems to deliver services for the targeted group to become resilient and prosper; and increased GoB investment in quality service provision to extremely poor households in the targeted communities; and GoB increases funding for programmes for livelihoods of extremely poor people. It is a holistic multidimensional development project with 03 major components i.e. Resilient Livelihood; Nutrition and Community Mobilization including 03 crosscutting issues of inclusion of Person with Disabilities (PWDS), Gender Equality and Climate Justice. WAVE Foundation is implementing the project in two vulnerable south west districts named Magura and Patukhali with the support of PKSF funding from the UK aid and the European Union. WAVE will directly serve more than 8000 extremely poor households in the selected vulnerable districts in the first phase (2020-2025).

4.7.2 Micro Entrepreneurship Project

WAVE has launched its Micro-entrepreneurship Program aiming at extending financial services to the progressive members of microfinance program for undertaking income generating activities that require bigger amount of capital. Micro-enterprise policy of WAVE is formulated based on assessing the needs and demands of the micro-entrepreneurs. Apart from progressive members of microfinance program, Micro-entrepreneurship Program provides financial services to all micro-entrepreneurs for

accelerating employment generation. Any business activity that has investment up to BDT 1.5 million (excluding land and building) is considered as microenterprise. An individual micro-entrepreneur can take loan up to BDT 1.0 million for his enterprise under this Program. In order to have a comprehensive impact on the lives and livelihood of the entrepreneurs, this program also imparts business development skill training and facilitates market linkage for the products produced by entrepreneurs through market system inclusion. In essence, this program intends to support and uplift the aspiring entrepreneurs in their pursuit of creating employments and income towards creating a prosperous Bangladesh.

4.7.3 Drought Tolerant Variety Rice Seeds Production & Marketing Project

The innovative project implemented under Learning and Innovation Fund to Test New Ideas (LIFT) Project of PKSf from July 2015 in Chuadanga District. The aim of the project to sustainable development and capacity building of the farmers through quality Drought Tolerant Variety Rice Seeds Production and supply for Aus and Aman season. The purpose of this project is to ensure availability the drought tolerant variety rice seeds, cultivation of the varieties and extend the rice seeds & technology in drought prone areas for ensuring maximum production. Under the project to provide useful, modern and environment-friendly production technologies, capacity building supports and establish market linkages of local commodities.

4.7.4 Promoting Agricultural Commercialization and Enterprise Project

The project is implemented under ‘Promoting Agricultural Commercialization and Enterprises (PACE) Project’ of Palli Karma-Sahayak Foundation (PKSF). PACE covers three complementary components financial services for micro-entrepreneurs, value chain development and technology & product adaptation aimed at increasing the income and generating employment of entrepreneurs through year-round onion cultivation in a sustainable manner. The project implemented by WAVE follows the strategy of combining financial & non-financial services and transfer of technologies to the micro-entrepreneurs involved in year round onion cultivation and value chain development. Its specific objectives are; increasing the income of project participants of year-round onion cultivation by ensuring availability of quality seeds & saplings; reducing the post-harvest wastages & production cost through establishing cost-effective commercial storage system at the farmers’ level and creating wage-based

employment through expansion of year round onion cultivation. The project is implemented in Mujibnagar Upazila of Meherpur district with the support of IFAD through PKSf.

4.7.5 Agriculture, Fisheries and Livestock Unit Project

Making the proper utilization of available household resources is the key for the development of agrarian Bangladesh. However, consequences of climate change and ever shrinking house resources as a result of rapid population growth require adoption of new technologies for maxim yield. Agriculture, Fisheries and Livestock Unit dedicates itself for testifying potential new technologies in agriculture, fisheries and livestock through setting demonstration at the beneficiary level for wider replication. The main purpose of the project is to extend sustainable technology and capacity building supports to the doorsteps of farmers with a view to increasing farming productivity and ensuring food security of the peoples. Supported by Palli Karma Sahayak Foundation-PKSf, this project extends both technical and financial support to the beneficiaries. Currently, this project works with 400 families.

4.7.6 WAVE Black Bengal Goat Breeding Farm Project

In 2008, WAVE Foundation started implementation of “Genetic Conservation of Black Bengal Goat and poverty reduction through increment of its productivity of family and breeding farm level” Project under LIFT project of PKSf. At the organization level, a goat breeding farm was established following Open Nucleous Breeding System (ONBS) to maintain and produce pure breeds of Black Bengal Goat while at the beneficiary level, the practice of scientific goat rearing was followed using semi intensive Macha method. The project was implemented during 2008 to 2010. Since then, Black Bengal Goat rearing has been incorporated with the mainstream microcredit program of WAVE and products have been designed based on the learning and insights of the project. One of the important features of this project was introducing & practicing practices the Semi Intensive Macha Method of goat rearing and ensure timely deworming & vaccination for goat which reduced goat mortality rate significantly from 40% to 10%. Another contribution of the project is scaling up of commercial Black Bengal Goat rearing at the beneficiary Level. In this regard, the project ensured door step veterinary services, breeding (buck) service, fodder cultivation and training of beneficiaries on scientific goat rearing management. As a result, a new project namely

“Alleviation of Poverty through Genetic Conservation and Increasing Productivity of Black Bengal Goat at Family and Breeding Farm Level” has been allocated in 2015-2016 fiscal year under LIFT of PKSF at Jamirtta, Manikgonj. Overall the project will contribute to reduce the goat mortality rate and increase the goat population as well as transformation into commercialization of Black Bengal Goat. WAVE implements the project in Chuadanga and Manikgonj districts with its own fund and support from PKSF.

4.7.7 Alleviation of Poverty through Rearing Hybrid Sheep Project

The aim of the project is to ensure food security of the poor and the hardcore poor through self-employment. Objectives of the project are to conduct necessary adaptive research to make the goat rearing profitable at household level and Demonstration farm level; to conserve the genetical purity of Local Improved and Hybrid Sheep; to help for developing the successful micro-credit borrowers as micro entrepreneurs in establishing small and medium-sized goat farms and to make the self-sufficient breeding farm at organizational level for providing training and technical assistance to the poor & the hardcore poor on a sustainable basis. WAVE implements the project in Pirojpur Union (Baradi Unit) of Meherpur Sadar Upazila in Meherpur district with the support of PKSF.

4.7.8 Income Generating through Dumba Rearing Project

The aim of the project is to ensure food security of the poor and the hardcore poor through self-employment. Objectives of the project are to conduct necessary adaptive research to make the Dumba rearing profitable at household and family farm level and to help to develop the successful micro-credit borrowers as micro entrepreneurs in establishing small and medium-sized dumba farms and to make the self-sufficient breeding farm at organizational level for providing training and technical assistance to the poor & the hardcore poor on a sustainable basis. WAVE implements the project in Damurhuda Upazilla (Koshaghata Unit) in Chuadanga district with the support of PKSF.

4.7.9 High Value Local Varsity Mixed Fish Culture Project and Fish Hatchery

The aim of the project is to promote availability of indigenous and high value fish species of Bangladesh like: mola, native singh-magur, pabda-gulsha etc. as well as

some extinct fish species like: Aire, Shoal, Gojar, Taki, Black Carp etc. The focus of this project is also to extent and develop sustainable fish culture technology in the rural area for generating additional employment opportunities in fisheries and ancillary sectors to alleviate poverty as well as improvement of farmer's socio-economic conditions. The project will help to create strong linkage among WAVE, GoB Fisheries Department at Upazilla & District level, others NGO, research institutions and local fish farmers. During the project period (03 years) demonstrations of indigenous and threatened fish species will be established at field level and soft loan will be provided among two hundred farmers for commercialization of different fish species. While at the organization level, a fish hatchery has been developed to preserve the indigenous fish species to preserve the fish variety as well as disseminate the valuable indigenous fish species in the beneficiary level. It is expected that it will be helpful to meet the local protein demand as well as making contribution to all over economy of the country. WAVE implements this project in three unions of Alamdanga Upazilla in Chuadanga district under LIFT Program supported by PKSF.

4.7.10 Sustainable Livelihood through Goat and Beef Value Chain Project

The overall goal of the project is to achieve sustainable livelihood of 1,500 smallholder farmers mainly through goat and beef value chain interventions by 2021. The activities are targeted to fulfilment of the targeted families through increase income and asset as per living income benchmark; increase availability and access to nutritious food; build resilient communities to combat climate change effects; empower women at family and community level and build social capital within the community. The project is implemented Hujuripara & Horipur Unions under Paba Upazilla in Rajshahi district and supported by Heifer International, Bangladesh.

4.7.11 Economic Enhancement through Beef and Goat Market System Project

The overall goal of the project is 'to achieve living income of marginalized and smallholder farmers by 2022 through developing beef and goat market system and creating self-propelled and sustainable producer's organizations. The activities are targeted to achieving of 'Market oriented production and productivity enhanced from baseline by the end of the project cycle; Increased awareness of improved hygienic processing and consumption of meat in the project locations within the project duration; Ensuring BDS for value chain actors through creating a one stop HUB and facilitating

entrepreneurship within the producers' organizations by the end of project; Enhanced capacity of community - based organizations for accelerating agro-enterprises by the end of project and Increased availability and access to nutritious food and improved sanitation by the end of project duration'. Since April 2018, the project has been implemented at Godagari Upazilla in Rajshahi district with the financial assistance of Heifer International Bangladesh.

4.7.12 Agro Entrepreneur Alliance –AEA Project

In Bangladesh, roughly half the population depends on agriculture for its livelihood. However, farmers face many challenges to earn a living. One of the challenges is access – access to technology, finance, markets, information related services and public goods. Another challenge is the lack of awareness of individual farmers of their basic rights. Collective voices & initiatives of farmers' alliance have the potential to address these challenges, increase & diversify production, marketing in a sustainable manner, improve food and nutrition security and act as major agents of change in Bangladesh. The goal of Agro Entrepreneur Alliance- AEA is to make the livelihoods of the smallholders sustainable by enhancing access to quality service, developing business sense and create awareness on the rights & entitlement of the farmers through collective actions. The project is being implemented in Chuadanga district.

4.7.13 Community Finance Program

WAVE continues and expands community finance program to ensure that it increases its outreach geographically and within the existing community it is serving through enhanced inclusion. Community finance plays a vital role towards transforming WAVE Foundation a sustainable institution for local communities. Through its multifaceted interventions under this program, WAVE aims to enhance outreach, coverage and inclusion, increased economic involvement and financial self-reliance, new and successful businesses in agriculture and other sectors. In Bangladesh, supply of capital or loan provided by government-private banks and financial institutions in case of informal sector is too little. In this backdrop, collateral free microfinance, a worldwide milestone program developed by the NGOs of Bangladesh contributes in economic development generating self-employment. WAVE implements its Poverty and Hunger Eradication Program to ensure self-employment through promoting socio-economic development of poor and lower-middle class people living in both rural and urban

settings. Under this program, 4 major loan products and various sub loan products play important role in agricultural production, livestock development including Black Bengal goat, local transportation, small to large scale business, enterprises and economic development in different sectors of organization working areas. The program emphasizes development of extreme poor and skill development training for program participants and technical assistance & medical services for their livestock development. In addition to financial services, WAVE intends to ensure integrated development of the program participants through incorporating health and education services along with awareness raising activities on social issues. Savings and micro insurance are one of the major activities along with loan support. Apart from this, WAVE has been working on cluster-based production and value chain development.

4.7.14 Accelerating Sustainable Water and Sanitation Facilities Project

Accelerating Sustainable Water and Sanitation Facilities for All-ACCESS supported by Water.org has been complementing to awareness raising and capacity building of community as well as sanitation entrepreneurs also. WASH Loan aims at behavioral change of the community people through promoting safe drinking water and sanitation practices; developing and enhancing the capacity of the WATSAN entrepreneurs to ensure the availability of water and sanitation products; providing the targeted community with affordable financial support for tube-well & sanitary latrine installation and establishing linkage with concerned government line agencies & other institutions for a sustainable sanitation facility.

4.7.15 Advancement of Informal Sector Employment Project

WAVE has started this project from June, 2020 with a view to obtaining some targets such as farmer's skilling up through training, reducing livestock mortality, reducing financial risk of livestock farmers and continue their encouragement on livestock farming. This project is being implemented among 52 units of WAVE out of 133 units under Chuadanga, Meherpur, Kushtia, Jhenaidah, Rajshahi and Manikganj districts. The farmers who receive loan for rearing livestock excluding poultry and pay a security fee are enlisted as project members. In dint of this payment, they receive some services like 100% waiver of loan status of the farm and its service charge, cash payment during claim settlement as rearing cost, executing free mass vaccination campaign for livestock and arranging training sessions for project enlisted farmers. With the support

of PKSF and SDC, this project is being implemented and will be continued till May 2024.

4.7.16 Strengthening Resilience of Livestock Farmers

In the aim of ensuring sustainable employment, the project is dedicated to increase capacity and productivity of micro-entrepreneurs who are existing beneficiaries under community finance program of WAVE Foundation. Youth from poor, marginalized and ethnic community in urban & peri-urban area in Bangladesh are covered under this project. It engages youth from low-income families and provides occupational based training as apprenticeship. The project is looking forward to providing Risk Management Training to 700 existing entrepreneurs who are affected by COVID-19 and Business Management, Risk Management and Occupational Training to 1300 rising entrepreneurs. Almost 500 youth from low-income family will be trained under 100 Master Craft Persons in informal sector. This project is being supported and funded by PKSF and World Bank. WAVE Foundation has been implementing this project through its 27-unit offices in 12 districts across the country.

4.7.17 Color Broiler and Pekin Duck Project

WAVE has started establishing color broiler chicken farm and executing other preparatory works for implementing this project in Chuadanga District from July, 2020. The aim of the project is to ensure nutritional security and poverty alleviation from the project area. The main purpose of the project to promote availability of climate tolerant color broiler chicken species and extension of the scientific technology method of color broiler chicken rearing among the small and medium family poultry Farmer. The main activities are divided into technical support, Specialized Flexible Loan and value chain development to upgrade the living standard of the targeted families through increasing their income and adaptation of the new species of hen. WAVE Foundation implements the project in Damurhuda Upazilla (Koshaghata Unit) in Chuadanga district with the support of PKSF.

4.7.18 Promoting Agricultural Commercialization and Enterprise (PACE) Project

WAVE started implementing this project under ‘Promoting Agricultural Commercialization and Enterprises (PACE) Project’ of Palli Karma-Sahayak Foundation (PKSF) from 2017 in Meherpur District. PACE covers three

complementary components- financial services for micro-entrepreneurs, value chain development and technology & product adaptation aimed at increasing the income and generating employment of entrepreneurs through year-round onion cultivation in a sustainable manner. The project implemented by WAVE follows the strategy of combining financial & non-financial services and transfer of technologies to the micro-entrepreneurs involved in year-round onion cultivation and value chain development. Its specific objectives are; increasing the income of project participants of year-round onion cultivation by ensuring availability of quality seeds & saplings; reducing the post-harvest wastages & production cost through establishing cost-effective commercial storage system at the farmers' level and creating wage-based employment through expansion of year-round onion cultivation. The project has been implemented in Mujibnagar, Meherpur sadar & Gangni Upazilla of Meherpur District and Ishwardi Upazila of Pabna District with the support of IFAD through PKSF.

4.7.19 Rural Micro-enterprise Transformation Project

WAVE has been implementing this project from January 2022 with the support of PKSF and IFAD. The goal of this project is to increase the income of marginal and small farmers and backward and forward market entrepreneurs related to meat and dairy sub-sectors, ensure food security and improve family nutrition. It intervenes to develop the value chain for safe meat and dairy products at different stages, value addition, expansion of financial services for the development of enterprises and strengthening of institutional structure. Initiatives are being taken to increase the range of enterprises and expand the enterprise through efficient production methods and strong market connections of marginal and small farmers. The project interventions primarily target (i) the poor, (ii) the transitional poor, and (iii) the enterprising poor. Among target groups, 30% are youth and at least 70% are women. This project is addressing some issues such as inadequate animal services, lack of quality cattle feed, conventional farm management, poor processing, lack of knowledge about safe meat and milk production and inadequacy of ICT and financial services in developing the market for safe meat and dairy products. It has 6 interventions i.e. 1: Livestock service market development and easier access to new and improved services locally through the development of LSPs, 2: Development of feed market by developing supply chain of high yielding raw grass, silage and ready feed through local suppliers along with concerned companies/institutions, 3: Farm mechanization by jointly developing dealers and sub-

dealers with the concerned companies, 4: Production of safe dairy products and entry into the premium market, 5: Safe meat production and entry into the premium market and 6 : Expansion of ICT and financial services. The project will involve 24,000 farmers and 1,000 service providers to strengthen the backward and forward markets during its period. WAVE is implementing this project in Damurhuda Upazila and Sadar Upazila of Chuadanga District; Mujibnagar Upazila, Sadar Upazila and Gangni Upazila of Meherpur District and Sadar Upazila of Jhenaidah District.

4.7.20 Safe Vegetables Production and Marketing Project

WAVE has started implementing this project from 2020 in Manikganj District. The aim of the project is to increase the sustainable income of local farmers and reduce consumer health risks by ensuring safe vegetables production and marketing using various technologies throughout the year on a commercial basis. The initiative is undertaken to create safe vegetable villages with local farmers for safe vegetables production. Use of environment friendly agricultural technology and vegetable production will promote health risks free safe vegetables throughout the year. The project interventions intend to increase the capability of targeted farmers to produce safe crops and extend agricultural technology to build reliable safe vegetables market management and ensure farmers' access to the market. Also public awareness will be raised on safe vegetables. The various activities under the project are- Farmers selection, formation of Farmers Producer organization and create safe vegetable production villages, Capacity Building (Training, Field Day Observation and Motivation Trips), Vegetables production using various technologies (GAP, IPM) for safe vegetables production, Distribution of agricultural inputs, Implement activities related to market linkage and development, Linkage with public-private service institutions (meetings and workshops), Ensure fund raising and financial support, Campaigning (setting up sign boards, making and distributing posters and leaflets, participating in various agricultural fairs, promotion in electronic media and maintain liaison, video documentation) and so on. The project is being implemented in Singair upazilla under Manikganj district with the support of PKSF.

4.7.21 Farmers' Producer Organization-FPO Strengthening Project

Farmers' Producer Organization-FPO (Krishi Morcha) model is a recognized body of smallholder farmers' that aims to improve the standard of their living and ensure a good

status of their available support, income, and profitability to promote small farming as a viable business. WAVE Foundation has been working to organize and capacitated farmers under its initiative of Farmers Producers' Organizations-FPOs concept named Krishi Morcha, in different regions in Bangladesh. This can be a potential model to improve the livelihood of the small and marginal farmers by evolving social capital and decentralize the existing exploitation in the agricultural supply chain such as middlemen resulting improved agricultural value chain. This initiative has a significant contribution towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs), in particular, Goals 1, 2 and 8. As of now, the WAVE Foundation reaches 425 farmers' doorstep with a total of 16 Krishi Morcha group in three districts of Chuadanga, Meherpur, and Manikganj. Farmers are trained and equipped with different input supplies, access to modern technologies, and a wider range of market information to sell their products at a fair price. Furthermore, they have been linked up with Government institutions for better access to government aid and support. More importantly, smallholder farmers are being capacitated providing information to the Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) and necessary action of the certification of their products. WAVE Foundation implements several projects on agriculture and livestock leveraging ICT tool for uplifting the livelihood rural farmers, safe vegetables production, Black Bengal Goat Rearing and involving Krishi Morcha groups with its own fund and funding form the Norec and PKSF.

4.7.22 Increasing Capacity of Poor Households Project

ENRICH is a program conducted at the grassroots level focusing for overall household development of the poor. The program targets poor families, working with them to enhance and maximize the utilization of their resources and skills. ENRICH aims to alleviate poverty not only through income generation but through a holistic approach targeting other crucial aspects of human life including health, education, youth development, community development, etc. This is a people-driven integrated development pursuit aiming at accelerating sustainable development. It also helps and creates mechanism for them to work with relevant institutions and larger communities for effectively preparing for responses to natural disasters and put in place a new and effective method of GO-NGO collaboration for development from below. WAVE implements the project in Jibonnagar & Damurhuda Upazilla in Chuadanga district and Singair Upazilla in Manikgonj district with its own fund and support from PKSF.

4.7.23 Loak Morcha Project

The Loak Morcha project aims to build capacity of the organized citizen groups so that they can raise voice to the local service (health, education, agriculture, social safety net and protect & prevent violence against women) delivery institutions & local administration; facilitating lobbying, dialogue, sharing meetings, public hearing, social audit etc. by the organized citizen groups to increase the access of mass community in mentioned GoB services and to increase the responsiveness of the local government, local level GoB service delivery institutions & local administration towards pro-people services. For achieving the program goal & objectives, the project intervenes the formation & awareness of ward level 54 Community Groups; capacity building training for Union Parishad Representatives; functioning of relevant Union Standing Committees); formation and capacity building of 21 People's Alliances (LoakMorcha) and mobilize them to undertaking advocacy initiatives towards responsive public services; conducting social audit and sharing findings with the respective GoB service providers & local administration; National level policy advocacy on field findings etc. WAVE implements the project in 18 Unions of Jibonnagar (08 UPs) & Singair (10 UPs) Upazillas in Chuadanga and Manikgonj district with its own fund and support from PKSF.

4.7.24 Youth Assembly Project

Youth Assembly (YA) is a platform of WAVE aims to empower young people and create a stronger community. The Assembly promotes youth rights and development as well as facilitates their active participation in social development. It brings the youths in a common space to broaden their views and values towards the positive social actions and changes. This space includes both physical and virtual platform for leveraging youths with the advents of learning from each other and fueling their actions. YA is conducting multi-faceted activities to accelerate youth participation in socio-economic development. The YA organized National Youth Rights Assembly to focus on the formulation of 'Effective National Youth Policy for Youth Rights and Development' as well as aiming at uniting youth under single umbrella to establish youth rights, particularly, right to education, skill and employment. Youth Assembly undertakes initiatives in different phases to combat the coronavirus and its resulting crisis through successfully running its 'Youth Against COVID19 Campaign'.

4.7.25 Out of School Children Education Program

The out of school children program aims ‘to create second chance education opportunities for out of school children ages between 8-14 years (dropped out or no enrolled in school yet) and bring them into mainstreaming education through non-formal education program’ and ‘to transform the students into productive citizen through providing technical or quality training those who successfully completion of the primary education’. For achieving those objectives, the program intervenes to conduct the baseline survey, learner selection, necessary materials supply, establishment and running of the learning center, formation and functioning of Center Management Committees-CMC, facilitate training & refresher training for the teachers, conduct grade final and PEC exams, organize sports & cultural events, day observance, conduct regular monitoring etc. WAVE Foundation implements the project in 02 Upazillas in Chuadanga district with financial support of Bureau of Non-Formal Education under the Ministry of Primary & Mass Education, the People’s Republic of Bangladesh.

4.7.26 Goat Raring for Urban Climate Migrants Project

GIZ has taken the initiative of Goat Raring for urban climate migrants and vulnerable Citizens to improve their resilient livelihood. The project’s goal is to improve the living conditions of climate migrants. Furthermore, empowering the vulnerable communities through expecting 70% women of the target group will be involved in the process. From this perspective, poverty reduction practices in Khulna city to improve the living conditions of climate migrants and vulnerable residents of the “hotspots” are developed by representatives of civil society organizations. In addition, the program is also drawing some probable Risk Factors and Overcoming Strategies about extreme climate incidents. It is strengthening household capacities to deal with climate-related risk alongside to ensure the relationship with market actors. The project is being implemented in Khulna City Corporation.

4.7.27 Strengthening Community Preparedness Project

It is a multi-country project. The purpose of the project is to reduce vulnerability and sufferings of communities affected by recurrent disasters in highly vulnerable areas in Asia (Bangladesh, Indonesia and Nepal) through enhancing capacities of stakeholders for disaster preparedness, response, and recovery. Bangladesh is one of the most

disaster-prone countries in the world due to climate change impact and also presenting its good performance in coping the natural disaster as a role model. Vulnerable communities are expected to be better equipped to co-lead on relief and recovery efforts in collaboration with local authorities. Hence, the specific objectives of the project are to enhance the capacity of the communities, disaster management committees, government and local and national humanitarian actors on response, recovery and disaster preparedness along with focus on increasing the capability of the women and youth on disaster response and make the disaster response committee more accountable to follow humanitarian standard. So that their roles can be sustained after the project period and learning can be shared widely. The major activities under the project are functioning union disaster management committee (UDMC), training for local leaders, and youth, to engage with government and other key actors to ensure that inclusive DRR is appropriately integrated into local plans. WAVE in partnership with Oxfam has been implementing this project in 6 Unions of Bakergonj Upazilla under Barisal district covering 5400 stakeholders.

4.7.28 Enterprise Development Program

With the motive of achieving rural development through a business-based approach, this project has been playing a significant role in improving livelihood and bringing development in rural areas. Bangladesh is at the threshold of growth centre development for farmers. Agro-based entrepreneur development in urban and rural areas is on board. In this backdrop, the project objective is to develop SME/ Medium enterprise in a sustainable approach to create positive social and environmental impact resulting in economic and employment opportunities for marginalized farmers, women and youth. It is working on identifying business opportunities, helping enterprises development and implementing viable business plans. Here, Enterprise is the major focus that can ensure substantial social impact. The project successfully able to link investors and entrepreneurs through a tailored package of loans, grants or bank guarantees to potential small-medium enterprises. The major activities are providing expert advice guidance sessions, trainings to small-medium enterprises, DEMO Plot Preparation, Promotional Campaigns, and Capacity Development Support for cooperatives besides monetary support market expansion, dealer & retailer Linkage. WAVE Foundation has been implementing this project in Barisal district since 2020 in partnership with Oxfam.

4.7.29 Renewable Energy Program

In the era of climate change and rapid environmental degradation, renewable energy in Bangladesh is revered for its ability to reduce the annual growth rate of GHG emissions from the fossil fuel-based power generation by exploiting Bangladesh's renewable energy resources for electricity generation. Renewable energy in Bangladesh refers to the use of renewable energy to generate electricity in Bangladesh. The current renewable energy comes from biogas that is originated from biomass, hydro power, solar and wind. Bangladesh has a success story in developing off-grid rooftop solar power known as solar home system (SHS) which has given electricity to a large number of people living in rather remote off-grid areas and who would not have electricity otherwise. More than four million SHS installed domestically have uplifted the lifestyle of these impoverished people by providing small-scale power at their homes. But in the context of national power demand and generation, the contribution of SMS is tiny, a mere 250 megawatt, which is only two percent of the total power generation capacity in the country. In fact, in the solar industry worldwide, large-scale solar power generation essentially means on-grid solar (grid-connected). Development Organizations along with private sector is playing the complementary role in the development of this sustainable and pro-people source of energy. WAVE's Renewable Energy Program constitutes of the following components and others:

Bio-gas and Bio-fertilizer

The overall objective of the project is to develop and disseminate domestic biogas in rural areas with the goal to establish a sustainable and commercial biogas sector in Bangladesh. It aims to reduction of workload of women, improvement in health and sanitation condition, increase agriculture production with proper utilization of slurry, employment generation, saving of conventional fuel sources such as firewood, agriculture residues and dries dung cake and reduction in green-house gas emission. IDCOL supports the project implementation in Chuadanga district.

Solar Home System

Now-a-days electricity is the right of the people. Our state is committed to provide electricity for all people and in every home. For promoting the green economy and natural conservation, WAVE is promoting solar power program emphasizing the people who are living in off grid area of the country. Major program interventions are Solar

Home System (SHS), irrigation and small industry. WAVE Foundation implements the project through partnering with IDCOL.

Improved Cooking Stove

The World Health Organization has estimated that 46,000 women and children die each year in Bangladesh as a direct result of exposure to indoor air pollution, while millions more suffer from respiratory diseases, tuberculosis, asthma, cardiovascular disease, eye problems, lung cancer etc. 70% of the victims of indoor air pollution are children under five. Estimated 90% of the rural household of Bangladeshi are using cow dung, jute sticks, other agricultural waste and wood for cooking and most use inefficient and poorly ventilated clay stoves that produce smoke, carbon monoxide and carcinogens. It is serious health threat for women and children. Due to these reasons WAVE Foundation has been promoting improved cooking stoves (BONDHU CHULA) at rural level through partnering with PKSf since 2010.

Solar Irrigation System

In the context of Bangladesh, extending affordable and sustainable agro-technologies to the poor farmers can play a transformative role in converting small farming into viable businesses and thereby making a measurable change in the gross agricultural production. The advent of eco-friendly renewable solar energy is widely recognized and very relevant to Bangladesh. WAVE Foundation launches solar irrigation systems for the broad base of poor small farmers who cannot afford the conventional costly irrigation system. Renewable Energy Development Program adopts a group approach that brings small farmers under a single umbrella who attain ownership of the solar irrigation system. Unlike conventional irrigation system, solar irrigation system diminishes wastages of water and land by devising an underground water canal for water circulation. The mandatory arsenic and TDS test prior to solar irrigation system installation makes it scientifically secured both for farming and the farmers (WAVE Foundation, 2022).

4.7.30 Dairy Value Chain Project

WAVE Foundation implemented "dairy value chain project" since 2021. It was the first dairy project in WAVE Foundation to embrace a value chain approach. It focuses on the entire dairy sector for sustainable pro-poor growth. It helps overcoming additional

challenges in the dairy sector such as unstructured milk collection and marketing systems, and an unavailability of and steep prices for inputs. Working in partnership with PRAN Dairy, to further redefine the way of milk production collection, and marketing in Baraigram Upazila, Natore, Bangladesh. The project focuses on implementing change through:

Figure -5: Dairy value chain

The project built household resilience, improved livelihoods, and helped chronically food insecure households which increased their income and dairy consumption. It focused on the following components of dairy value chain:

Components of the Dairy Value Chain Project

Increasing Access to Inputs

As generally farmers were not well aware of benefits of the deworming and vaccination as well as improving cattle health and better feeding practices, the project undertook

different set of activities. To increase access to dairy inputs and services, the project worked through expanding and connecting input shops, LHW, and AI services with the farmers in the project area. The project recruited and trained LHWs providing cattle health services to project producers. The project devised by setting up a micro franchise-based input shop network which was geared towards delivering high-quality, affordable, and timely agricultural inputs to rural smallholder producers.

Improving Productivity

Bangladesh as a whole has one of the lowest yields of milk in the region with daily milk per cattle ranging from 2-5 litres. Thus, productivity is a major aspect for dairy farmers which is critical for small holder farmers in the northern part of Bangladesh. Improving productivity was thus a major concern for the project. The project is providing training on “Advanced Farm Management and DFT Awareness Training,” that focused on animal husbandry and nutrition, disease management, and gender awareness.

The capacity building process was carried out by trained Farm Leaders (FLs), Livestock Health Workers (LHWs), Artificial Insemination (AI) workers and collection point managers. PRAN Dairy was also engaged in educating dairy farmers on dairy nutrition and management.

Increasing Access to Markets

Smallholder farmers were deprived of fair prices in many cases due to the distance from market as well as the over reliance on the milk collectors who would offer lower prices. To circumvent this, the project established a dairy hub model enabled with the chilling plants.

The project also ensured that the collection points functioned well as trainings were provided on business operation and technical aspects. It helped to establish a model, where collection points were able to sell the collected milk to multiple buyers including local market actors, such as sweet makers and other processors. This opened up the market for collection points as now they could collect greater volume of milk and also sell to a wider range of buyers by reducing their dependency on a single buyer (Dairy Value Chain Project Proposal 2023).

Key Activities of the Dairy Value Chain Project

Sl	Activities
01	Formation of dairy producer groups.
02	Provide improved dairy management training among farmers.
03	Organize vaccination and animal health camp.
04	Orient dairy farmers on the production of improved fodder.
05	Provide seed and cutting support for producing improved variety of fodder.
06	Provide training to local livestock doctors for improving technical services.
07	Build partnership with veterinary medicine companies for making quality animal medicine available in the community.
08	Establish strong relationship with upazila livestock office for facilitating quality services.
09	Provide training to milk collectors and processors for ensuring hygiene in the milk supply chain.
10	Establish partnership with private milk collection companies for ensuring fair prices of milk.

(Source: Dairy Value Chain Project Proposal, 2023)

Chapter - 05: Analysis of the Dairy Value Chain Project

5.1 Key Impacts of the Project Interventions

The analysis reflects the perceptions and opinions of the 20 dairy farmers, 10 inputs sellers particularly feed sellers, 10 local animal doctors, 10 milk collectors and processors on the overall impacts of the dairy value chain project from the dairy value chain project area, Baraigram Upazila, Natore.

5.1.1 Farm size of the dairy farmers

In the project area, there exists different size of the dairy farms. The data presented in the chart provides an overview of the dairy farm size.

Chart - 01: Dairy farm size of the farmers

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

It is presented in the chart that out of 20 farmers, more than half of the farmers (60%) have between 02-05 dairy cows. An only 20% farmers have cow below 02 cows as well as above 05 dairy cows. That means that most of the farmers in the project areas usually rear between 02-05 dairy cows.

5.1.2 Sale volume of dairy feed seller and income from feed sale

The feed sellers who were interviewed are very happy by saying that the project has helped them to expand business and increase customers through creating increasing demand of feed from dairy farmers.

Chart - 02: Has monthly sale volume of dairy feed seller and income from feed sale increased after project intervention?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

The chart illustrates that out of 10 feed sellers, most of them (70% respondents) expressed their opinion that their monthly income and sale volume of dairy feed has been increased over the time after project intervention. Only 20% respondents expressed negative impacts and 10% respondent did not disclose their opinions.

5.1.3 Sale volume and income of local animal doctors

Through project activities in building the technical and business management capacity of the local animal doctors as the first line of modern veterinary advice to the smallholder producers has been successfully accepted. The animal doctors are now based locally and are readily available whenever the producer needs them for accessing services. The animal doctors trained by project have experienced a significant increase in clients and income since their technical skills have vastly improved.

Chart - 03: Has monthly sell volume and income of local animal doctors increased after project intervention?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

The figure presents that the income of 80% local animal doctors has been increased significantly where only 20% expressed that their income did not increase over the time after implementing dairy value chain project.

5.1.4 Farmers knowledge improvement on dairy management

The producers report that overall better and improved management practices are very necessary for establishing dairy farms profitable. The project has built the capacity and knowledge of the dairy farmers through different types of services and capacity building trainings.

Chart - 04: Has dairy value chain project improved farmers knowledge on dairy management?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

It is presented in the chart that 80% of the respondents expressed their opinions that the dairy value chain project has tremendously improved their knowledge on improved dairy management whereas only 20% farmers told that their did not improve their knowledge due to various reasons.

5.1.5 Increasing milk production of the dairy farms

As project provided different sorts of inputs and services such as capacity building for improved farm management, deworming, vaccination, ready services from animal doctors, it contributed a lot for increasing daily milk production per cattle over the time;

Chart – 05: Has milk production of the dairy farms increased after project intervention?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

The chart presents that almost all the farmers (90%) agreed that the production of their dairy farms has been increased tremendously after getting connected with the project and only 10 farmers thought that their farm production has not been increased over the time after project intervention.

5.1.6 Higher price of milk

The project worked with dairy value chain actors at different levels for creating a synergy and consistency between supply and demand side dynamics of dairy milk at the project area that eventually ensures farmers getting higher price.

Chart - 06: Does the farmers get higher price of milk now than before?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

It is explained in the chart that most the farmers (70%) get higher price of milk now than before the project intervention and only 10 % farmers told that they don't get higher price now and only 20% farmers did not share their opinions.

5.1.7 Increasing income of the farmers from dairy cow

As dairy farmers capacity and knowledge has been enhanced, production has been increased and milk price has been adjusted, all of these factors eventually contributed a lot to shift farmers income to higher level.

Chart - 07: Does the income of the farmers increase from dairy cow after project intervention?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

The chart explains that most of the farmers (70%) strongly agreed that their income has been increased from dairy farm after project intervention and 10% farmers disclosed negative responses and 20% farmers did not make any comment on this.

5.1.8 Collecting more milk by collectors and processors

Collectors maintain good relationships with both formal and informal processors. Their relationship is also based mainly on the amount of milk delivered and timely payment made. Since project trained collectors to supply quality milk timely and with no milk spoilage, – business transactions have thus improved and collectors and processors are collecting more milk now.

Chart - 08: Do collectors and processors collect more milk now after project intervention?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

It is presented in the chart that almost all collectors and processors (90%) collect more milk after project intervention. It is because that the project has undertaken a number of activities such as improved shed, feed, management, vaccination of animal for increasing milk production. Only 10% participants did not disclose their opinion.

5.1.9 Collectors and processors getting available milk

The business of collectors along with formal and informal processors has been expanded over the time after project intervention. The knowledge and capacity of doing business has been improved tremendously along with producers capacity. That's why they are getting available milk as per their daily demand in the market.

Chart - 09: Do collectors and processors get available milk as per their demand now?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

It is found that almost all collectors and processors (90%) get available milk now as per their daily requirement due to project intervention. Only 10 collectors and processors did not agree that they get available milk.

5.1.10 Improved quality of milk

Milk quality is a big concern for the processors as well as final consumers. And increasing amount of fat percentage in the milk is one of significant parameters of quality. As the project worked with all dairy value chain actors for creating high quality product as well as competitive market, the quality of milk has been improved significantly.

Chart – 10: Do collector and processor think that milk quality has been improved after project intervention?

(Source: Interview Survey 2023)

It was found that milk quality particularly fat percentage of milk has been improved over the time after project intervention. 80% collectors and processors agreed that milk quality has been improved tremendously and only 10% respondents showed negative response and 10% respondents were not interested to disclose their opinions.

5.2 Additional Impacts of the Project Interventions

5.2.1 Changes at inputs and services level

Producers contact the animal doctors by phone who advises immediately on what to do or the animal doctors pays a house call. The skills of the animal doctors has improved after receiving training from the project and in addition to giving good treatment, they also advice on dairy management. The project has made artificial insemination services more available and affordable for most of the project producers.

Vaccination is given to cows in group. The farmer leader contacts the animal doctors and sets a date and place for vaccination, after which it is duly carried out. Availing of vaccination in a group reduces the cost per cow.

The quality feed is more readily available locally at project-selected feed shops. Fodder cultivation seem to have gained widespread popularity in the project area that it should have. Even though most producers report that the feeding practice of fodder increases milk production.

5.2.2 Changes at milk production level

The study found that farmers continued to practice several aspects promoted by the project such as practicing better husbandry, improved feeding, and medicine usage. There is an initial increase in number of milking cattle. Daily milk production per cattle has been increased over time;

5.2.3 Changes at milk processing level - informal

Sweetshops, ghee-shops and tea-shops compete with other processors to get their required supply. The milk price in the informal market is therefore usually higher than the chilling plants since demand is high most of the year.

5.2.4 Changes at milk processing level - formal

The project has supported the formation of producer groups and connected them to forward market actors, namely milk collectors. The notion was simple: local level entrepreneurs are supported to act as aggregators of milk. Such entrepreneurs are supported with technical training and a digital fat testing device to test milk quality providing a fair market value of the product. Such collectors are linked with chilling

plants of PRAN dairy. Chilling plants thus are linked to the collectors. The chilling plants benefitted from gaining access to a large farmer base, where they can get bulk amounts and provide services to the suppliers as per their policies and requirements.

5.2.5 Changes at milk collection and transport level

Processors collect individually from collectors who collect milk from producer groups in bulk. Both processors and collectors report that they get the milk supply timely. Improvements in the collection system are perceived in the quality of milk which has improved and the mode of collection. Project collectors wait at a fixed location for milk collection where the producers supply the milk and so the collectors do not have to go door to door. Also since project has oriented the project collectors on safe and hygienic collection and transport of milk, milk spoilage is no longer a major issue as it was prior to project. Collectors find it convenient to procure milk in group and likewise disburse payments similarly. Collecting milk in bulk allows them to pay the group producers an average price.

5.2.6 Changes at milk chilling level

Chilling plants are enjoying high volumes of milk from the collection points that are supported by the project. Given the increasing price of fresh milk over the years, one may say that the price of the local market is more lucrative for farmers in many cases, as milk quality is not a core determinant of price in the local market. It is noted that the case of side selling to local markets and other processors have increased significantly. The local market has also become more competitive.

5.2.7 Changes at consumption level

The project also carried out activities for raising awareness on quality milk and milk products consumption among final consumers. The amount of milk consumption at household level has also been increased after project intervention. On the other hand, milk processors received intensive training for producing milk products with maintaining highest hygiene standards. That's why milk and milk related products consumption has been increased significantly over time (Interview Survey 2023).

5.3 Weaknesses of Dairy Value Chain Project

Though the dairy value chain project has carried out a number of exciting impacts on the business of different value chain actors, it has also some weaknesses that were evident after collecting data directly from project beneficiaries. The project did not focus on the following weaknesses:

- Low level farmers knowledge on milking hygienically;
- Still there are local breed cow which have low productivity;
- Lack of appropriate technology for dairy farm management;
- Lack of proper milk storage system at farm level;
- Lack of low cost and reliable cow breeding service;
- Long calving interval of dairy cows.
- Poor bio-security at the dairy farm level;
- Poor waste management practice adds pollution;
- Unavailability of quality animal vaccine year round;
- The high cost of dairy animal feeds.

Chapter - 06: Conclusion

6.1 Findings of the study

From the analysis of data, it is clearly evident that dairy value chain project possesses a number of positive impacts and changes whereas there are weaknesses that should be incorporated into the major findings of the study.

Dairy farming has been established as profitable business venture. A large number of dairy farms has already established in the area. The farmers are interested in crossbreeds thereby increasing the genetic of cows. Cross breeding dairy cow population is also increasing day by day. Even, the financial institutions are investing to support the dairy farms. Women farmers are very active in dairy management at household level in the project area.

In addition, knowledge of the farmers on improved dairy management has been increased with project support. Milk production of the dairy farms has been increased after project intervention. Price of the milk has also been higher now in comparison to before. That's why the income of the farmers from dairy cows has been increased after project intervention. Even, the sales of dairy feed and income of feed seller and local animal doctors has been increased positively. The quality of milk has been improved due to feeding practice such as concentrates feeding and improved management. Collecting and processors are collecting more milk now than before due to increasing demand of milk related products form consumers.

On the other hand, the dairy value chain project has a number of weaknesses that should be overcome for improving the project further next time. The most important shortcomings are lack of farmers knowledge on hygiene milking, lack of appropriate technology for farm management such as chuff cutter, milking machine etc, lack of low cost and reliable cow breeding service, quality vaccine and high cost of animal feed. Poor bio-security at the farm level and poor waste management were major weaknesses.

The identified positive impacts and weaknesses of the dairy project will be taken into account in order to pave the way of profitable dairy farming in the project area.

6.2 Recommendations

The dairy value chain project has achieved a large number of exponential impacts whereas it has encountered a number of challenges or shortcomings. For improving the dairy value chain project further, the positive impacts should be continued whereas the weaknesses should be overcome successfully. Following recommendations are imperative in order to overcome the shortcomings and improve the project:

- Dairy farmer knowledge on hygiene milking should be enhanced with appropriate training;
- High yielding dairy cows and cultivation of green grass should be promoted;
- Updated technology like milking machine, cream separator, chopping machine, electric/hand cutter should be introduced;
- Low cost technology to be introduced for milk preservation at farm level;
- Ensuring availability of quality concentrated feeds, fodder, vaccine and artificial insemination at the competitive price;
- Calving interval of the dairy cow should be shortened with appropriate treatment and management;
- Introduce farm level bio-security and waste management system;
- Developing new marketing channel for fair price of milk;
- Fresh to pasteurized milk may be introduced;
- Different value added milk products should be introduced;
- Control mastitis by providing appropriate technology and creating awareness;
- Department of Livestock Services should be strengthened with adequate number of dairy extension workers to provide technical services;
- Ensuring easy access to finance or low cost finance for dairy farming;
- Composting, bio-gas project may be introduced among the dairy farmers;

6.4 Conclusion

Dairy value chain project plays pivotal role in developing the dairy sub sector which subsequently contributes to build the economy of the country. Milk, the nature's most perfect food for building intelligent nation is coming from this sector. Annual milk production of the country is far below the normal requirement. At present we are producing only 9.95 MMT of milk annually but our requirement is 13.32 MMT (DLS

2022). Bangladesh has to increase milk production up to 1.5 times to meet the national demand. The major constraints to milk production are lack of genetically improved dairy cows, high cost of feeds and fodder, poor management and lack of appropriate technology for dairy farm management. We found that more than half of dairy farms have between 02 -05 dairy cows which indicates that development of small-scale farming operations remains at a very early stage. High yielding dairy cows and cultivation of green grass should be promoted whereas modern technology like milking machine, cream separator, chopping machine, electric/hand cutter should be introduced immediately. For creating market of milk and milk related products, it is imperative to develop new marketing channel for fair price of milk, to introduce fresh to pasteurized milk and different value-added milk products.

REFERENCES

1. BER. (2022) Bangladesh Economic Review. Ministry of Finance. Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.
2. CARE (2023), Strengthening the Dairy Value Chain Project: Stories of Impact, CARE Bangladesh.
3. Dangour, A.D.; Green, R.; Häsler, B.; Rushton, J.; Shankar, B. and Waage, J. (2021)' Linking Agriculture and Health in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: An Interdisciplinary Research Agenda', Proceedings of the Nutrition Society, 71.2: 222–28.
4. DLS. (2021) Department of Livestock Services. Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, Government of Bangladesh.
5. DLS. (2023) Department of Livestock Services. Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, Government of Bangladesh.
6. FAO (2022) Declaration of the World Summit on Food Security, Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
7. Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO). (2022) FAO corporate document repository on, “Poverty alleviation and food security in Asia: role of livestock”. Originated by: Regional Office for Asia and the Pacific.
8. Haque, S. A. M. A. (2021) Improved Market Access and Smallholder Dairy Farmer Participation for Sustainable Dairy Development, LESSONS LEARNED STUDY, BANGLADESH.
9. Hemme, T., Garcia, O. and Khan, A. R. (2020) A review of milk production in Bangladesh with particular emphasis on small-scale producers. Pro-Poor Livestock Policy Initiative (PPLPI), 2005.
10. Islam M. N. and Akbar M. A. (2022) Current dairy feeding and management systems. Hand book of Dairy Nutrition Bangladesh. P–31–49. Published by American Soybean Association.
11. Jabbar, M.A. (2022) Policy Barriers for Dairy Value Chain Development in Bangladesh with a Focus on the North West Region , Dhaka: CARE Bangladesh
12. Joshi, P.K. (2022) Agricultural Diversification and Smallholders in South Asia. Pages 626. Ahmedabad, India.
13. Lien do, T.K. et al. (2022) 'Impact of Milk Consumption on Performance and Health of Primary School Children in Rural Vietnam', Asia Pacific Journal of Clinical Nutrition 18.3:326–34.

14. MOFL. (2022) Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock. Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock. Annual Report.
15. Muehlhoff, E.; Bennett, A. and McMahon, D. (2020) Milk and Dairy Products in Human Nutrition, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Rome.
16. Neumann, C. and Rogers, L.M. (2021) 'Contribution of Animal Source Foods in Improving Diet Quality and Function in Children in the Developing World', Nutrition Research 22.1-2: 193-220.
17. Raha, S. R. (2022) Status of Dairy Production and Marketing in Bangladesh: Milk Marketing System. P-17-30. Hand book of Dairy Nutrition Bangladesh. P-31-49. Published by American Soybean Association.
18. Saadullah. M. (2020) Smallholder dairy production and marketing in Bangladesh. Paper presented at south-south workshop on smallholder dairy production and marketing. NDDB-ILRS, Ahmedabad, India, 13-16 March, 2020.
19. WAVE Foundation. (2022) Annual Report, Dhaka.
20. WAVE Foundation. (2023) Dairy Value Chain Project Proposal, Dhaka

APPENDIX

Interview Questionnaire

This study is undertaken in order to get better understanding of the dairy value chain project implemented by WAVE Foundation in a comprehensive and effective manner. We assure you that the information/data collected will be kept confidential and no individual data shall be made public in any manner. The final report would present the data only in aggregate form and no individual name will be mentioned anywhere.

Date: Time:.....

1. Respondent's Name with Address:
 2. Age
 3. Sex.....
 4. Literacy level of owner's (√)
 - i) Illiterate ii) Primary iii) Class 6-10
 - iv) S.S.C v) HSC vi) B.Sc. vii) Above B.Sc.
 5. Mobile No:
 6. No of years in dairy farming/business
 7. Main source of income (√)
 - i) Dairy farming ii) Business iii) Agriculture iv) Others
 8. What are the strengths of dairy value chain project in your area?
Response.....
 9. What are the changes achieved due to dairy value chain project in your area?
Response.....
 10. What are the weaknesses of dairy value chain project in your area?
Response.....
 11. Do you suggest any recommendations for improving dairy value chain project?
 12. Response.....
- Farmers Specific Questions
13. How many dairy cows do you have in your farm?
 - i) Below 02 cow ii) 02-05 cow iii) Above 05 cow
 14. Has dairy value chain project improved your/farmers knowledge on improved dairy management?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

15. Do you have improved housing shed of the dairy cow?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

16. Do you cultivate improved variety of fodder for dairy cow feeding?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

17. Do you practice vaccination of the dairy cow?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

18. Do you practice Artificial Insemination for cow breed improvement?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

19. Has milk production of the dairy farms increased after project intervention?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

20. Do you get higher price of milk now than before?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

21. Has your income been increased from dairy cow after project intervention?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

22. What do you feel about dairy farming? Is it profitable?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

Questions for local feed seller

23. Has your monthly sell volume of dairy feed and income from feed sale increased after project intervention?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

Question for local animal doctors

24. Has your monthly sell volume and income of local animal doctors increased after project intervention?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

Questions for collectors and processors

25. Do you collect more milk now after project intervention?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

26. Do you get available milk as per their demand now?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

27. Do you think that milk quality has been improved after project intervention?

i) Yes ii) No iii) No Opinion

-Thank you so much for your time-